

THE VALUE RELEVANCE OF ESG PERFORMANCE DISCLOSURE

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Abstract: Using a sample of 2,310 firm year observations over the 2008-2022 period, we provide the first evidence on the impact of ESG performance disclosure on share price in Nigeria. We find that ESG performance disclosure is more likely to reward share price performance. Consistent with the signaling theory, we find that this result is in line with the Global Reporting Initiatives (2006). This study points to a promising direction for future research to gain a deeper understanding of how ESG performance disclosure of corporations affect their share price asymmetry.

Keywords: ESG performance disclosure, Nigeria, value relevance.

Introduction

The maximization of shareholders' wealth remains the central goal of corporate financial managers (Cooper & Petry, 1994; Davies, 2018; Dusan Mramor, 2001; Fatemi et al., 1983; Jones & Felps, 2013; Kumar & Charles, 2009; Omodero & Amah, 2017; Onwumere et al., 2012; Ozuomba et al., 2016; Windsor & Boatright, 2010). Among several ways to achieve this goal is to improve share price of companies. This study seeks to determine whether ESG performance disclosure could signal improvement in share price, which in turn could signal increase in firm value.

A number of empirical studies have shown concerns on fluctuating company share price, particularly, in developed countries (Al-Shubiri, 2010; Chughtai et al., 2014; Dissanayake & Wickramasinghe, 2016; Kaizoji & Miyano, 2019; Maslov & Mills, 2001; Nguyen et al., 2020; Palágyi & Mantegna, 1999; Plerou et al., 1999; Tandon & Malhotra, 2013; Wang et al., 2013). These interests are yet to be seen in emerging countries, of which Nigeria is one. This scenario explains the rationale for this current study.

This paper investigates how the equity market values corporate ESG activities. This is an important undertaking from several perspectives. First, in order for markets to work efficiently, prices of goods, services, and assets should reflect all available information. If ESG performance truly affects firm value, it should be capitalized into stock prices. On the other hand, if ESG performance does not affect stock prices, it can be inferred that stock market participants do not consider ESG activities to be value relevant. Given the recent popularity of socially responsible investment funds and indices, it is of great interest to these investors to know whether companies' ESG activities are reflected in stock prices.

Measurements of ESG activities are often clouded with ambiguity. While its broad classification suggests an all-encompassing term, the concept of ESG encompasses a diverse array of issues that large companies face in today's global business environment. ESG activities occur on a scale that ranges from managing potential risk factors to developing sustainable activities that address issues at their core. This heterogeneity of ESG issues presents challenges for investors and academic researchers when attempting to measure a given company's ESG activity. Unfortunately, there currently does not exist a standardized ESG rating system, and researchers have used a variety of techniques to measure ESG activities. This paper seeks to shed light upon the effects of ESG activities using a methodology derived from previous research on corporate social performance and its financial effects.

The market participants and investors worldwide are giving increasing importance to business's environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance. As of February 2020, over 80% of the Fortune Global 500 companies issued reports on ESG performance, and a staggering 93% of the countries reported having ESG regulated policies and initiatives (Zhang et al., 2020). This shows increasing awareness in ESG worldwide. One of the key reasons for this phenomenon is because ESG is viewed as a measurement of sustainability and ethical impact of an investment or a company's business practices (Cheng et al., 2015).

The determination of sustainability has never been more important in recent history than it is today. With the global warming crisis and issues related to social welfare and corporate scandals, the world is becoming increasingly aware of issues affecting humanity and the earth, and leaders and corporations are being pushed to consider more than just profits. ESG is a tool that not only measures current sustainable factors but also a guide and a standard that will drive behavior and performance to be at a sustainable level.

The importance of ESG can be seen from how it is a factor in reducing risk and increasing transparency of an investment or a company. Kotsantonis et al. (2019) write that ESG performance is a factor in reducing the variability of investment returns and is already being used by mainstream investors and credit rating agencies as a guide to risk and return. This is because ESG initiatives often affect costs of capital and a company's financial performance. For example, an environmentally friendly company may be successful in cost-saving of raw materials and energy in production and will be less affected by constantly variable energy prices. This creates a lower risk of investment in the company's stock.

ESG also increases transparency and information, and this, in turn, reduces perceived risk of investment and increases the valuation of a company (Friede et al., 2015). This has been seen with how ESG rating is used as a guide in credit rating assessments and how companies with good ESG are now said to pay less to say the same thing in relation to investor relations and public relations costs. The remaining part of this paper covers literature review, methodology, results and discussions, conclusions and recommendations.

Literature Review

This section provides theoretical, conceptual and empirical literature of the study. In terms of theoretical framework, signaling theory provides the theoretical foundation of this study. Signaling Theory is a fundamental concept in the fields of economics and organizational theory, particularly relevant in situations where information asymmetry exists between two parties. Originally developed in the context of labour markets by Michael Spence (1978), it has since been applied broadly, including in finance, marketing, and corporate governance.

The core of Signaling Theory involves two parties: one that has specific information (the signaler) and another that does not but is trying to infer it (the receiver). The theory addresses situations where one party possesses information that others do not have. This imbalance often leads to inefficient market outcomes. In order to overcome this asymmetry, the informed party sends a signal, a noticeable action or attribute that conveys information about themselves to the uninformed party. However, effective signals usually incur a cost, which is crucial for the credibility of the signal. The cost ensures that only those who genuinely possess the desired attributes or capabilities can afford to send the signal. For a signal to be effective, it must be observable and interpretable by the receiver. The receiver must be able to notice the signal and correctly deduce the information being conveyed.

Signaling can significantly impact market dynamics. It can lead to a separation of markets (e.g., separating high-quality from low-quality products) and influence consumer behaviour, investment decisions, and hiring practices. However, in some cases, extremely confident or high-quality signalers might engage in counter-signaling, where they deliberately avoid traditional signaling methods to stand out. The theory is sometimes criticized for its simplifications and assumptions, like rational behaviour and cost structures. Additionally, in some cases, too much signaling can lead to a clutter of signals, making it hard for receivers to distinguish genuine signals from noise. In summary, Signaling Theory provides a powerful framework for understanding how information is conveyed in situations where not all parties have access to the same information. Its applications extend far

beyond its initial economic context, providing insights into a wide range of social and business interactions, like in the instant case. Furthermore, the signaling theory is used in this paper to guide the analytical framework in Figure 1, showing the interplay among the independent variable (ESG), Ohlson Model (EPS, DPS, and BVEPS), and control variables (firm size, profitability, listing age, and leverage).

Figure 1. The Analytical Framework

Source: The Authors (2024)

In terms of conceptual literature, environmental performance involves GHG emissions, energy use and efficiency, air pollutions, water use, waste management, use of ecosystems, innovations in environmental products, etc. Social performance involves the workforce, workplace health and safety, customer health and safety, diversity and equal opportunity, poverty and community impact, supply chain management, training and education, customer privacy, etc. Similarly, governance performance involves code of conduct and business principles, accountability, transparency and disclosure, executive pay, board diversity, and structure, bribery and corruption, stakeholder engagement, shareholder rights, etc.

In line with the Ohlson Model (1995) and extant empirical literature, earnings per share (EPS) is defined as profit after tax divided number of ordinary shares. In addition, dividend per share (DPS) is defined as cash dividend paid divided by numbers of shares. Book value of equity per share (BVEPS) is defined as total equity divided by number of ordinary shares. Share price is defined as the average share price as at the opening and closing date. Firm size is defined as natural logarithm of total asset. Profitability is defined as return on equity, which is defined as profit after tax divided by total equity (%). Listing age is defined as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange. Leverage is defined as total liabilities divided by total asset.

In terms of empirical studies, for example, Semenova et al. (2010) provide insight into how environmental and social performance is reflected in the market value of listed SIX 300 companies on OMX Stockholm. Applying the Ohlson valuation model, they express the market value of equity as a function of the book value of equity, accounting earnings, and environmental and social performance, where the last two variables are the proxies for other value relevant information. They test this model with data from the GES Investment Services® risk ratings that enable them to create a holistic view on the long-term extra-financial performance and to disaggregate the effects of various dimensions of environmental and social performance on stock prices. The evidence presented in this study finds support for the value relevance of environmental performance at both aggregated and sub-aggregated levels. In the social dimension, support is found for community and supplier relations.

Jain et al. (2016) examine whether short sellers, as informed investors, take into consideration corporate social responsibility (CSR) performance and disclosure in the areas of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) sustainability in making investment decisions. They find that firms' market value measured by price per share is lower. They detect a negative association between ESG

scores and short selling, indicating that short sellers avoid firms with high ESG scores and tend to target firms with low ESG scores.

Miralles-Quirós et al. (2018) analyse whether social responsibility activities carried out by companies listed on the São Paulo Stock Exchange during the 2010–2015 period play a significant role in enhancing firm value. Their overall results support the value enhancing theory rather than the shareholder expense theory. However, it is important to note that the results also show that the market does not significantly value the three ESG pillars. Specifically, the market positively and significantly values the environmental practices carried out by companies not related to environmentally sensitive industries. In contrast, the market positively and significantly values the social and corporate governance practices carried out by the companies belonging to these sensitive industries.

Bernadi and Stark (2018) investigate the relationship between the levels of disclosures on environmental and social activities and performance (analyst following) and subsequent analyst following (subsequent levels of disclosures on environmental and social activities and performance). They do so to investigate the value relevance of information about environmental and social activities and performance. Their evidence was consistent with their value relevance and an associated demand for, or general interest in, such disclosures from informed market participants. They also argue that their results suggest positive links between analyst following and the *quality* of environmental and social disclosure.

Zuraida et al. (2018) investigate the impact of environmental, social and governance (ESG) disclosure by companies around the world on market value. Using a large sample of non-financial companies listed in 38 countries during the period 2008–12, they test for value relevance by employing the modified version of the Ohlson (1995) model developed by Collins, Pincus and Xie (1999). They find support for the value relevance of disclosure of ESG both in aggregate form and for its individual components. Furthermore, Aras et al. (2018) evaluate Turkish banks' multidimensional corporate sustainability performance and whether banks' sustainability efforts are value related during the years 2013 and 2015. The results of this study are insignificant in the ongoing debate on whether Turkish banks' sustainability efforts are value related. However, a significant and positive relationship has been found between the financial sustainability performance and the market value in the long run.

Yoon et al. (2018) analyze whether a firm's corporate social responsibility plays a significant role in promoting its market value in an emerging market, namely Korea. They employ environmental, social, and corporate governance (ESG) scores to evaluate CSR performances and examine their effect on firm valuation. They find that CSR practices positively and significantly affect a firm's market, in line with previous studies on developed countries. However, its impact on share prices can differ according to firm characteristics. For firms in environmentally sensitive industries, the value-creating effect of CSR is lesser than for firms that do not belong to sensitive industries. Specifically, corporate governance practice negatively influences the firm value of environmentally sensitive firms. Further, governance practice significantly promotes market value, while investors do not significantly value governance practice carried out by other firms.

Kirkerud and Tran (2019) investigate the value relevance of environmental, social and governance performance for stock prices in Europe. The analysis was conducted using the Ohlson price model, which allows us to examine the association between ESG and stock price, where stock price is a function of financial and non-financial information. They apply a data panel of 5354 firm-year observations during the period 2011 – 2017 collected from the Thomson Reuters Eikon Database. The sample consists of 791 companies in member countries of the EU and EFTA. Their results indicate that ESG performance is value relevant for stock prices in Europe.

Handayani (2019) analyzes the value relevance of ESG disclosure on both aggregate and singular aspects. The study employs sensitivity analysis to assess any differences in the value relevance of both models. The findings show that environmental, social, and ESG disclosure have significant impacts on share prices and stock returns, therefore they have value relevance in both price model and return model. Only governance disclosure has no effect on both share prices and stock returns.

Aureli et al. (2020) examine the relationship between a company's sustainability practices and its

financial performance has been investigated with different methods and from different theoretical perspectives. This study aims to answer the following questions: (a) Do investors react to the publication of sustainability reports on company websites? (b) Has the market reaction to the publication of the sustainability report increased in the last few years? In this study, 170 report disclosures were considered from 55 listed companies from all over the world in the period from 2009 to 2016; 33 different event windows were analyzed. Results show two significant event windows and an increasing level of significance in the reports released after 2013.

Halimah et al. (2020) investigate whether information content on sustainability reporting has a significant association with listed companies share price. They also assess the difference effect of sustainability reporting adoption in the mandatory and voluntary context in developing countries, particularly in Malaysia and Indonesia for several reasons provided. The final sample was 43 firms in Indonesia and 57 firms in Malaysia. The data in this study used secondary data obtained from Thomson Reuters Datastream. To examine our hypothesis, they apply regression model. The result of this study provides evidence that information on sustainability reporting has significant association with firm's price.

Bolibok (2021) empirically investigates the impact of social responsibility performance on the value relevance of financial data in the Polish banking sector. The research employs multivariate regression analysis based on the Ohlson model and the Chow test for structural breaks. The examined sample covers 154 bank-year observations of 17 banks listed on the Warsaw Stock Exchange from 2009–2020. The results suggest that financial disclosures of banks included in CSR indices are generally more value relevant. Additionally, more responsible banks exhibit higher (lower) responsiveness of market values to net earnings (book values of equity) compared to their less socially responsible counterparts.

Santos (2021) analyses the association between Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and market data, more concretely share prices and stock returns, for companies listed in the STOXX Europe 600 Index, from 2010 to 2019 period. To measure CSR was used the ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) overall score from Refinitiv and its three components: Environmental Score, Social Score, and Governance Score. The modified Ohlson model proposed by Barth and Clinch (2005) was used to study the price model, while the modified Ohlson model proposed by Ota (2005) was used to study the return model. Results suggest a positive association between CSR and market data, but in most models, especially in the price model, these are not statistically significant. Nevertheless, a statistically significant association between market data and changes in ESG scores was found. An additional robustness test suggests that the financial crisis impacted the relationship between CSR and market data.

Danielsen and Johansen (2021) develop a methodology that enables investors to differentiate between two types of companies: those with high performance on ESG issues that have the potential to significantly impact value, and those with high performance on ESG issues that do not have the potential to significantly impact value. They find that an investment strategy based on taking a long position in companies with a high ESG score when ESG is value relevant and a short position in stocks with a high ESG score when ESG is not value relevant generates superior performance, as measured by the Sharpe ratio and the Fama French 5-factor alpha extended with the liquidity factor.

Lazopoulou (2021) attempts to broaden our horizons in understanding whether there are any actual value creators among the multiple dimensions which compose the rating in ESG performance. Utilizing a sample of 1.429 firm-year observations of European corporations and by employing a linear-price model that correlates the market value of equity and the different aspects of ESG combined score. The findings of this study support that ESG performance has market valuation implications, while some ESG dimensions are more statistically significant than others.

Al-Hiyari and Kolsi (2021) examine whether ESG performance provides shareholders with value-relevant information to help them in their equity pricing decisions. Using a cross-country sample of non-financial firms drawn from 10 Middle East and North African (MENA) countries between the period from 2013 to 2019, they find evidence, which is based on the price specification of Ohlson (1995) valuation model, that ESG performance practices are positively priced by market participants and add incremental information content to earnings and book value of equity (BVE). However,

when we split the aggregate ESG performance into its components, governance practice was found to be more value relevant than social practice, while the environmental pillar was found to be value (ir)relevant to shareholders.

Zumente and Bistrova (2021) detect how ESG adds value to the long-term shareholder value creation and to discover whether businesses are aware of positive ESG effects of publicly listed Central and Eastern European (CEE) companies are compared to their decade-old versions. The content analysis results show that companies with higher sustainability awareness ensure shareholder value creation via improved financial performance, management quality as well as reduced risk metrics. Additionally, qualitative nonfinancial factors such as reputation, stakeholder trust, employee satisfaction and engagement provide an even more significant effect on the long-term value than the pure financial matters.

Vander Bauwhede and Van Cauwenberge (2022) investigate the determinants of sustainability report (SR) assurance and whether this assurance is value relevant within the context of the European Union (EU), where, under the Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD), sustainability reporting is mandatory for large public interest entities (PIE) as of fiscal year 2017. Using a sample of 1832 firm-year observations from 660 European listed companies over the period 2017–2020, the results of a logistic regression analysis indicate that firm size, environmental, social and governance (ESG) performance and industry affiliation are important drivers of the demand for SR assurance. The value relevance regressions suggest that SR assurance was positively associated with the stock market value.

Abuaja and Ukpong (2022) assess the value relevance of sustainability reporting of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria of 12 companies. Findings of the study show that environmental, social and corporate governance disclosures, taken together and individually are value relevant and have effect on the market value of firms. Also, Chan et al. (2022) study the association between environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance and the value relevance of accounting information. They use 6,486 firm-year panel data to analyze the data from 723 non-financial Chinese firms covering a period of 10 years (2011–2020). Their results reveal that ESG performance decreases the value relevance of accounting information.

Furthermore, Jeong-Ho and Kim (2023) examine the incremental effects of the environmental, social, and governance rating on accounting information regarding R&D expenditure of 3,449 firm-years of Korean manufacturing firms listed on the Korean Stock Exchange (KSE) for 2012~2021 years. Results show that higher ESG ratings increase the value relevance of development costs, but not research costs. Furthermore, Sahlian et al. (2023) examine the value relevance of ESG scores (environmental, social and governance) before, during, and after tumultuous economic periods (including the 2008 financial crisis and the COVID–19 pandemic) taking into consideration a company's financial performance. The analysis, using Ohlson's price model, was based on a sample of companies listed on European stock exchanges from 2003 to 2021. The results underline that, after each tumultuous economic period, there was a decline in the value relevance of ESG scores and an increase in investor focus on company financial performance.

Kim and Martowidjojo (2023) provide preliminary analysis on the value relevance of ESG disclosure in Indonesian listed banks. The study observes a sample of five listed banks in the period 2009-2019. Using multiple regression analyses, the study finds that ESG disclosure has a value relevance. The finding was robust, even after controlling for internal and market performance of the bank. Further analysis shows that the social component of ESG was the driver of the value relevance of ESG in banks. The remaining part of this paper covers methodology, results and discussions, conclusions and recommendations, references, acknowledgements, and disclaimer on conflict of interest.

Methodology

This section covers the research design, population, sample size, model specification, sources and methods of data collection, methods of data analysis, post estimation tests, and acceptance or rejection criterion. The research design adopted in this paper is *ex post facto* research design, which means that the events discussed have already happened and recorded. Thus, the data used by this study is historical data. Furthermore, the population and sample size of the study are the same,

consisting of the 154 publicly listed firms on the Nigerian Exchange (see Table 1).

Table 1. Population/Sample Size

Serial	Sector	Number
1	Agriculture	6
2	Conglomerates	6
3	Construction/Real estate	9
4	Consumer goods	21
5	Financial services	47
6	Healthcare	8
7	Information & communications technology	8
8	Industrial goods	13
9	Natural resources	4
10	Oil and gas	10
11	Services	22
	Total	154

Source: Extracts from NGX (2024)

A multiple regression model was adapted from the work of Ohlson (1995) in order to capture ESG performance disclosure and the four (4) control variables (firm size, profitability, listing age, and leverage).

$$\text{SHPR}_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ESG}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \text{EPS}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{DPS}_{i,t} + \beta_4 \text{BVEPS}_{i,t} + \beta_5 \text{FSIZ}_{i,t} + \beta_6 \text{PROF}_{i,t} + \beta_7 \text{LAGE}_{i,t} + \beta_8 \text{LEVG}_{i,t} + \mu_{i,t} \dots \dots \text{equation (1)}$$

Whereas SHPR is the average share price of firm *i* at time *t* of opening and closing date, ESG is environmental, social and governance performance of firm *i* at time *t*, EPS is earnings per share firm *i* at time *t*, DPS is dividend per share firm *i* at time *t*, BVEPS is book value of equity per share of firm *i* at time *t*, FSIZ is firm size of firm *i* at time *t*, PROF is profitability of firm *i* at time *t*, LAGE is listing age of firm *i* at time *t*, and LEVG is leverage of firm *i* at time *t*, β_0 is the model constant, β_{1-8} are beta coefficients to be estimated, *i* is firm script, *t* is time script, and μ is the idiosyncratic error term. Thus, Table 2 provides the variables and their measurements, and a priori expectations.

Table 2. Measurements and Signs

Serial	Variable	Description	Sign
1	Y, SHPR, Share price	Measured as average of opening and closing share price of firm <i>i</i> , at time <i>i</i>	
2	X ₁ , ESG, Environmental, Social and Governance	Measured based on the Global Reporting Initiatives (2006) and the framework provided by Kolsi (2018)	+
3	X ₂ , EPS, Earnings per share	Measured as profit after tax divided number of ordinary shares.	+
4	X ₃ , DPS, Dividend per share	Measured as cash dividend paid divided by numbers of shares.	+
5	X ₄ , BVEPS, Book value of equity per share	Measured as total equity divided by number of ordinary shares.	+
6	X ₅ , FSIZ, Firm size	Measured as natural log of total asset.	+
7	X ₆ , PROF, Profitability	Measured as earnings before interest and taxes divided by total equity (%).	+
8	X ₇ , LAGE, Listing age	Measured as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange.	+
9	X ₈ , LEVG, Leverage	Measured as total liabilities divided by total asset.	-

Source: The Authors (2024)

Thus, our a priori expectations are stated as follows:

$X_1 > 0$, means that an increase in ESP performance, will lead to an increase in share price.

$X_2 > 0$, means that an increase in EPS, will lead to an increase in share price.

$X_3 > 0$, means that an increase in DPS, will lead to an increase in share price.

$X_4 > 0$, means that an increase in BVEPS, will lead to an increase in share price.

$X_5 > 0$, means that an increase in FSIZ, will lead to an increase in share price.

$X_6 > 0$, means that an increase in PROF, will lead to an increase in share price.

$X_7 > 0$, means that an increase in LAGE, will lead to an increase in share price.

$X_8 > 0$, means that an increase in LEVG, will lead to a reduction in share price.

Furthermore, the sources of data are annual financial statements of the sampled firms. Several authors used financial statements in their studies (). Financial statements are formal instruments of communication between a firm and its stakeholders. In Nigeria, the Companies and Allied Matters Act of 1990 (as amended) requires companies to publish their accounts within a maximum period of six (6) months after the end of a financial year. Also, the methods of data analysis include descriptive analysis, correlation analysis, multiple regression analysis, and post estimations. The post estimation tests include test for multicollinearity, test for heteroskedasticity, test of model fitness, coefficient of determination (R^2). Section three ends with the level of significance test accepted in this study, which is 5 percent (.05). The remaining part of this paper include the results and discussions, conclusions and recommendations, references, acknowledgements, declaration on no conflict of interest between the authors.

Results and Discussions

This section covers the results, which include descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, multiple regression results and post estimation tests results. Table 3 provides a summary of descriptive statistics. Table 4 provides the results of correlation analysis and Table 5 provides a summary of multiple regression analysis and post estimation tests results.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
SHP	2,310	9.86	10.268	.5	46.09
ESG	2,310	79.317	5.332	56.6	91.6
EPS	2,310	1.355	1.524	.03	8.3
DPS	2,310	.407	.522	0	2.16
BVEPS	2,310	.929	.26	.61	2.05
FSIZ	2,310	8.936	.434	8.05	9.72
PROF	2,310	7.119	35.184	-233.11	110.69
LAGE	2,310	22.86	15.606	2	49
LEVG	2,310	87.145	15.451	69.02	203.27

Source: STATA 18.4 Outputs

As indicated in Table 3, the number of observations is 2,310, representing 15 years multiplied by 154 firms, and the mean of share price is ₦9.86, the mean of ESG is 79.317, the mean of EPS is 1.355, the mean of DPS is .407, the mean of BVEPS is .929, the mean of firm size is 8.936, the mean of profitability is 7.119 percent, the mean of listing age is 23 years, and the mean of leverage is 87.145 percent. Furthermore, the standard deviation (spread) of share price is ₦10.268, representing a major deviation from the mean ($10.268/9.86 = 104.14$ percent), which supports a study on share price asymmetry. The spread of ESG is 5.332, which is low when compared with its mean ($5.332/79.317 = 6.7$ percent), which is a stable solution to the volatility shown by share price, the spread of EPS is 1.524, the spread of DPS is .522, the spread of BVEPS is .26, the spread of

firm size is .434, the spread of profitability is 35.184 percent, the spread of listing age is 16 years, and the spread of leverage is approximately 15.45 percent.

In addition, the minimum mean of share price is 50 kobo, the minimum mean of ESG is 56.6, the minimum mean of EPS is .034, the minimum mean of DPS is 0, that is, some firms, in some years, did not pay dividend, the minimum mean of BVEPS is .61, the minimum mean of firm size is 8.05, the minimum mean of profitability is -233.11 percent, the minimum mean of listing age is 2 years, and the minimum mean of leverage is approximately 69 percent. Finally, the maximum mean of share price is ₦46.09, the maximum mean of ESG is 91.6, the maximum mean of EPS is 8.3, the maximum mean of DPS is 2.16, the maximum mean of BVEPS is 2.05, the maximum mean of firm size is 9.72, the maximum mean of profitability is 110.69 percent, the maximum mean of listing age is 49 years, and the maximum mean of leverage is approximately 203 percent.

Table 4. Correlation Matrix

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
(1) SHPR	1.000								
(2) ESG	0.537*	1.000							
	(0.000)								
(3) EPS	0.597*	0.076	1.000						
	(0.000)	(0.356)							
(4) DPS	0.653*	0.082	0.569*	1.000					
	(0.000)	(0.319)	(0.000)						
(5) BVEPS	0.249*	0.030	-0.042	-0.016	1.000				
	(0.002)	(0.716)	(0.609)	(0.849)					
(6) FSIZ	0.258*	-0.036	0.478*	0.537*	-0.467*	1.000			
	(0.001)	(0.659)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)				
(7) PROF	0.259*	-0.038	0.086	0.233*	0.015	0.218*	1.000		
	(0.001)	(0.646)	(0.298)	(0.004)	(0.859)	(0.007)			
(8) LAGE	-0.085	-0.048	0.081	-0.080	-0.166*	0.322*	0.002	1.000	
	(0.298)	(0.556)	(0.324)	(0.328)	(0.043)	(0.000)	(0.984)		
(9) LEVG	-0.106	0.107	0.024	-0.122	0.449*	-0.120	-0.083	0.124	1.000
	(0.197)	(0.192)	(0.766)	(0.137)	(0.000)	(0.145)	(0.314)	(0.129)	

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 18.4 Outputs

As indicated by the results in Table 4, the bivariate association between ESG and share price is positive (.537) and significant (.000). In the same vein, the bivariate association between EPS and share price is positive (.597) and significant (.000). Also, the bivariate association between DPS and share price is positive (.653) and significant (.000). Similarly, the bivariate association between BVEPS and share price is positive (.249) and significant (.002). In terms of the control variables, the bivariate association between firm size and share price is positive (.258) and significant (.001). Similarly, the bivariate association between profitability and share price is positive (.259) and significant (.001). In contrast, however, the bivariate association between listing age and share price is negative (-.085) and significant (.298). In the same vein, the bivariate association between leverage and share price is negative (-.106) and significant (.197).

Table 5. Results of Multiple Regression Analysis

GMM estimation

Number of parameters = 8

Number of moments = 8

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 2,310

GMM weight matrix: Robust

SHPR	Beta coefficient	z	p>z
ESG	2.537001	4.50	.000
EPS	2.047002	4.48	.000
DPS	8.393004	5.24	.000
BVEPS	14.59003	3.41	.002
FSIZ	3.59980	3.90	.001
PROF	.028667	3.92	.001
LAGE	-.009950	-0.34	.298
LEV	-.087028	-0.51	.197
Constant (β_0)	79.21021	9.24	.000
R ²	60.32%		
Prob>Chi ²	.000		
Hettest	.000		
Mean VIF	1.66		

Source: STATA 18.4 Outputs

As indicated by the results in Table 5, ESG shows a positive statistically significant effect on share price, that is, it is value relevant. Also, perhaps in line with the Ohlson Model (1995), EPS, DPS, and BVEPS are all value relevant. However, on the control variables, only firm size and profitability are value relevant. Listing age and leverage are not value relevant. The results of ESG, EPS, DPS, BVEPS, firm size, and profitability are in consistent with our a priori expectations. In contrast with our a priori expectation, listing age was negative. We had expected that with experience gained over time, listing age would bring positive bearing on share price. Leverage as expected shows negative effect on share price. As expected, highly geared firms are not expected to show improvement in share price, their immediate interest is survival. Overall, this ESG result is mixed, it is consistent with past empirical results (Abuaja & Ukpong, 2022; Al-Hiyari & Kolsi, 2021; Aureli et al., 2020; Bolibok, 2021; Danielsen & Johansen, 2021; Handayani, 2019; Jain et al., 2016; Jeong-Ho & Kim, 2023; Kim & Martowidjojo, 2023; Kirkerud & Tran, 2019; Lazopoulou, 2021; Miralles-Quirós et al., 2018; Sahlian et al., 2023; Santos, 2021; Semenova et al., 2010; Vander Bauwhede & Van Cauwenberge, 2022; Yoon et al., 2018; Zumente & Bistrova, 2021; Zuraida et al., 2018).

Conclusions and Recommendations

This study examines the value relevance of ESG performance disclosure among the 154 publicly listed firms on the Nigerian Exchange (NGX). The number of observations was 2,310, representing 15 years multiplied by 154 firms, and the mean of share price was ₦9.86, the mean of ESG was 79.317, the mean of EPS was 1.355, the mean of DPS was .407, the mean of BVEPS was .929, the mean of firm size was 8.936, the mean of profitability was 7.119 percent, the mean of listing age was 23 years, and the mean of leverage was 87.145 percent.

Also, the bivariate association between ESG and share price is positive and significant. In the same vein, the bivariate association between EPS and share price is positive and significant. Also, the bivariate association between DPS and share price is positive and significant. Similarly, the bivariate association between BVEPS and share price is positive and significant. On the control variables, the bivariate association between firm size and share price is positive and significant. Similarly, the bivariate association between profitability and share price is positive and significant. In contrast,

however, the bivariate association between listing age and share price is negative and significant. In the same vein, the bivariate association between leverage and share price is negative and significant. On the basis of the GMM multiple regression analysis, this study has found that ESG performance disclosure has significant impact on share price performance. This is supported by the findings of other works. ESG performance disclosure was seen in this work as consisting of environmental, social and governance performance. Furthermore, based on the correlation analysis, this study has found that ESG governance has significant relationship with firm share price performance. From this study, it is observed that the increasing ESG performance has positive impact on firm's share price performance. The main reason may be due to the Signaling Hypothesis. Furthermore, during this study, several ideas and potential research areas have been identified. Only 15 years data were taken for the study (2008-2022), therefore, the data set could be extended for robust estimations. Also, there are several control variables that are available in the literature. However, this study considers only 4 variables (firm size, profitability, listing age, and leverage), more variables may be considered. Furthermore, ESG was considered in this study as an aggregate. In future studies, researchers may consider disaggregating ESG into its three components (environmental, social, and governance).

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Conflict of Interest

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